

3. Melodic Mysticism: Exploring the Fusion of Tantra Philosophy in the Navavarana Ragamalika of Muthaiah Bhagavata

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1. Introduction

Carnatic music and Tantra share a profound connection that intertwines art, spirituality, and culture. This connection is rooted in the ancient traditions of South India and has shaped the evolution of Carnatic music over the centuries. Tantra philosophy is an ancient Indian philosophical tradition that encompasses a wide range of beliefs, practices, and rituals rooted in the idea of harnessing divine energy, using it for spiritual transformation and liberation. One notable example is Muthaiah Bhagavata's composition 'Svarnakarshana Ganapate,' which serves as a bridge between Tantra philosophy and classical music. This composition showcases an intricate understanding of Tantra concepts and represents a capsule of Navavarana kritis by Muthuswami Dikshitar, highlighting the integration of Tantra philosophy into a musical composition.

1.1 About the Composer

Muthaiah Bhagavata, a distinguished artiste in Carnatic music during the 19th-20th centuries (1877-1945), excelled as a musician, composer, Harikatha Bhagavata, and Lakshanakara. His mastery of ragas, talas, and innovative compositions showcased a profound understanding of Carnatic tradition alongside creative flair. Bhagavata's repertoire spanned diverse musical forms across Sanskrit, Telugu, Kannada, and Tamil, including Varnams, Kritis, Ragamalikas, and Thillanas, with the creation of numerous new ragas. Revered for both musical brilliance and profound lyrical content, his compositions were deeply influenced by Vedic, Shastraic, and Sangita knowledge, reflecting a seamless blend of poetic expression and musical intricacy.

1.2 About Ragamalika

Literally, 'Ragamalika' means, a garland of Ragas and this belongs to the sphere of both kalpita Sangita (Varnam, Kirtana, Kirti etc.) as well as Manodharma Sangita (Alapana, Tanam, Svarakalpana etc.). In a ragamalika composition, each section is in a different raga and if used as a raga mudra, the names of ragas are cleverly interwoven into the sahitya so that the meaning is not disturbed. Usually, there is an appropriate chittasvara passage in the respective raga, followed by a makuta svara, before the pallavi is sung.

The number of ragas handled in the composition is generally pre-fixed to the name of the composition (Pancha, Nava, Chaturdasa, Nakshatra, Ashtottarasata etc.).

A string of villoma chittasvara (reverse order), with ragas used in the composition, are usually sung at the concluding section. Ragamalikas are of different categories ranging from simple to complex types.

1.3 Yantra, Mantra, Tantra and Sri Chakra

In Hindu religion, any materialistic or spiritual accomplishment involves three religious components clothed in symbols which are the means, the method and the end (Rao), represented as-

- a diagram or design (Yantra)
- a formula or an equation (Mantra)
- Its function (Tantra)

In other words,

Yantra : Yantra is an instrument/apparatus/geometrical design which is embedded with powers in itself. It is a form, pattern or design of requisite disposition, arrangement, adjustment and control of the powers of the Mantra. Yantra is a symbolic representation of the essence of Deity.

Mantra : Mantra is a form of sound energy composed of certain letters, embedded with some seed sounds/syllables known as bijaksharas and it protects those who recite or chant it.

Tantra : Tantra is the method of worship and it expounds or elaborates knowledge of mantra, yantra and their applications. It is defined as the science esoteric and art of realisation.

In the Tantra Sastra, Yantra and Mantra are described as the two aspects by which a practitioner achieves the desired goals.

Sri Chakra : Sri Chakra is a geometrical diagram employed in the worship of Goddess Tripura Sundari, according to Tantric Rituals. It has a great significance in the Sakti worship tradition and is said to have mystic powers.

Sri Chakra is constituent of 'Nine enclosures' or veils called '**Nava Avaranas**' visualised as an elaborate mansion or abode of Goddess Tripura Sundari. Each of the enclosures has its own name, shape, deities, puja krama, prakriti, bija, nature, tattva, sthayi, rasa and alphabet associated with it, each of which is regarded as a step in our journey to the sanctum.

विंदुत्रिकोणवसुकोणदशारयुग्म |
 मन्वस्त्रनागदलषोडशपत्रयुक्तं |
 वृत्तत्रयं च धरणीसदनत्रयं च |
 श्रीचक्रराज उदितःपरदेवतायाः ||

The nine enclosures and chakra names are –

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|---|----------------------|---|------------------------------|
| 1. A Square | - | Bhupura | - | Trailokya Mohana Chakra |
| 2. 16 petalled lotus | - | Shodasa Dala Padma | - | Sarvasa Paripuraka Chakra |
| 3. 8 petalled lotus | - | Ashta Dala Padma | - | Sarva Sankshobhana Chakra |
| 4. 14 triangles | - | Chaturdasara | - | Sarva Saubhagyadayaka Chakra |
| 5. Outer 10 Triangles | - | Bahirdasara | - | Sarva Sadhaka Chakra |
| 6. Inner 10 Triangles | - | Antardasara | - | Sarva Rakshakara Chakra |
| 7. 8 triangles | - | Ashta Kona | - | Sarva Rogahara Chakra |
| 8. 1 Triangle | - | Trikona | - | Sarva Siddhiprada Chakra |
| 9. Dot | - | Bindu, central point | - | Sarva Anandamaya Chakra |

2. Objective of the Study

Among the popular compositions written with regard to the concept of 'Navavarana' are - Oothukkadu Venkata Subbaiyer's 'Kamakshi Navavarana Kritis' and Muthuswamy Dikshitar's 'Kamalamba Navavarana Kritis'. While both these were individual compositions on each chakra, Muthaiah Bhagavatar has authored a 'Navavarana Ragamalika', encapsulating the essence and elements of each chakra in the various sections of a single composition. This study is a humble attempt of exploring the Fusion of Tantra Philosophy in the Melodic Ragamalika composition of Muthaiah Bhagavatar enriched with the Mystic elements of Sri Chakra, which is a fine example of the mastery of the composer over mantra sastra and different chakras and avaranas of Devi. As there is a **gap in research** of this lesser explored composition, it has been taken up for the present study.

3. Methodology

Though not exhaustive, this research has been done as a qualitative and analytical study to demonstrate fusion of knowledge and spirituality of this composer with reference to aesthetic musical values and an exposition of the Tantric doctrines which describe the ways in which the divine energy can be kindled. The sources for literature review include books, journals, audio recording and articles published on various web-based discussion forums.

4. 'Navavarana Ragamalika' - Musical and Literary Analysis

This ragamalika reverses the Navavarana-s of the Sri Chakram and consists of 11 sections, each composed in a different Raga and set to Adi Talam. Evoking Bhakti rasa, the composition begins with a salutation to Lord Ganapati - 'Svarnaakarshana Ganapate', in the raga Dhanyasi followed by Nine Charanam segments, each devoted to one Avaranam of the Sri Chakram. The ragas used for these are - Mohana, Vasanta,

Bhairavi, Kambhoji, Todi, Kalyani, Athana, Surati and Saurashtra. The eleventh and the concluding segment is the Mangala Charanam, appropriately composed in the auspicious Sri Ragam. The composer cleverly employs different vibhaktis (declensions) for each section, as seen in Dikshitar's Kamalamba Navavarana series. Here are a few observations from the sahitya of the composition :

Section 1 : Pallavi - Ganesha Stuti - Dhanyasi Ragam

पल्लवि : स्वर्णाकर्षण गणपते सुगुणधनासिम दयानिधे करुणामृतायित |
नवावरण शुभ गानकृतौ शक्तिं देहि सुमते ||

**Section 2 : 1st Avaranam – Trailokya Mohana Chakram-Mohana Ragam
(Prathama Vibhakti – Nominative Case)**

चरणं 1 : त्रैलोक्यमोहनचक्राधीश्वरि त्रिपुरादिकोणगाते विभास्वरि |
आलोकमात्रेण अणिमादि दायिनि अंबा कुमारि मामवतु भवानि ||

**Section 3 : 2nd Avaranam – Sarvaasapuraka Chakram - Vasanta Ragam
(Dvitiya Vibhakti – Accusative Case)**

चरणं 2 : सर्वाशापूरकचक्र निवासिनीं साधु भव संताप विनाशिनीं |
निर्वाणसौख्यदां निर्मलां त्रिमूर्तिं नीरजासिनीं भजे निरंजनकीर्तिं ||

**Section 4 : 3rd Avaranam – Sarva Sankshobhana Chakram - Bhairavi Ragam
(Trtiya Vibhakti – Instrumental Case)**

चरणं 3 : अनंगकुसुमादि अष्टशक्तियुतया अखिल संक्षोभणचक्र निरतया |
अनंगाद्युपासिते कल्याणि हित्वया अनिशं रक्ष्य ते जगत् भैरविनुतया ||

**Section 5 : 4th Avaranam – Sarva Saubhagyadayaka Chakram - Kambhoji Ragam
(Chaturdhi Vibhakti – Dative Case)**

चरणं 4 : सुकुमार रोहिणी पदायै नमोखिल सौभाग्यदायकांभोदींदेवे नमो |
बहु मनुकोणनिलयायै नमो नमो भासुरहीर वलयायै न ||

**Section 6 : 5th Avaranam – Sarva Sadhaka Chakram – Todi Ragam
(Panchami Vibhakti – Ablative Case)**

चरणं 5 : काळीतोडीयते नमे मनस्सुखि कामितसर्वार्थसाधकि नायकि |
ललितनादस्वरूपधराय लास्यनवाधार विश्वंबराय ||

- Section 7 : 6th Avaranam – Sarva Rakshakara Chakram – Kalyani Ragam
(Shashti Vibhakti – Genitive Case)
- चरणं 6 : दशकलात्मकवहिनत शारदे सकलरक्षाकरचक्र विराजिते |
दशबले कल्याणि चंडिकादेवि ते दासोहं दशमुद्रासेविते ||
- Section 8 : 7th Avaranam – Sarva Rogahara Chakram – Athana Ragam
(Saptami Vibhakti – Locative Case)
- चरणं 7 : शाम्भवि त्वयी भक्तिं सततं मे देहि सर्वरोगहरचक्रेशं एहि |
जंबूनतनिभे सकल वशंकरि समय वृताटन मोहं शंकरि ||
- Section 9 : 8th Avaranam – Sarva Siddhiprada Chakram – Surati Ragam
(Ashtami Vibhakti – Vocative Case)
- चरणं 8 : निरुपममहिमे दुर्गे निरंजनि निखिलसिद्धिप्रदचक्रसुरंजनि |
सुरटीकितगुणे शोकनिवारिणि शुभमयि गुरु शिवदेहविहारिणि ||
- Section 10 : 9th Avaranam – Sarva Anandamaya Chakram – Saurashtra Ragam
- चरणं 9 : सकलानंदमयचक्रनिवासे सच्चिदानंदविंबविकासे |
अखिलागमनुते अंबा सुभद्रे मोदय सौराष्ट्रं मोदसमुद्रे ||
- Section 11 : Mangala Charanam – Sri Ragam
- चरणं 10 : नवावरणश्रीरागमालां नवां समर्पितां स्वीकुरु तव लीलां शिवे |
श्रीचामराजमहीषे दिश मण्गलं सदा श्रित हरिकेशे ||

The composition is a devotional invocation to various forms of the divine feminine, particularly focused on the nine Avaranams, or layers of spiritual consciousness. It praises the divine qualities and protective powers of each deity, from the first Avaranam where the goddess reigns over the universe's allure to the ninth Avaranam, embodying ultimate joy and bliss. The verses are rich in imagery and symbolism, depicting the goddess in her various manifestations and emphasizing her omnipotence and benevolence. The composer seeks blessings for composing a song that will be like nectar to the ears, honoring the goddesses' grace, purity, and ability to fulfill desires. The devotion is expressed through vivid imagery, invoking the goddesses' forms, their dwelling places within the chakras, and their significance. The composition culminates in a humble offering, seeking blessings for auspiciousness and divine grace.

We can see that this piece is a codification of the Navavarana kritis of Muthuswami Dikshitar comprising 11 kritis. Many resemblances can be found in the selection of words for this composition.

4.1 Mudra-s featuring in this composition

a. Raga Mudras

There is a cleverly built-in Raga Mudra in each of the eleven sections of this Ragamalika – a few Suddha and then a few Suchita Mudra-s. Some of these are straightforward phrases like Mohana, Bhairavi, Kalyani, Saurashtra and Sri. For the remaining raga-s, we find the typical Dikshitar-like constructions - **sugNa dhanAsima** (for Dhanyasi), **bhava santApa** (for Vasanta), **kambhOdIndavE** (for kambhoji), **kALItODIyatE** (for Todi), **samayav.rtaTana** (for Athana), and **suraTIkagunE** (for Surati).

b. Chakra Mudra

The chakra names of each Avarana are entwined in the lyrics of this composition as - Trailokya Mohana Chakra, Sarvaasaapuraka Chakra, Sarvasamkshobhana Chakra, Sarva Saubhagyadayaka Chakra, Sarvartha Sadhaka Chakra, Sarvarakshakara Chakra, Sarvarogahara Chakra, Sarvasiddhiprada Chakra and Sarvaanandamaya Chakra. Thus, Chakra mudra occurs in each section.

c. Vaggeyakara Mudra

The Vaggeyakara Mudra (composer's signature), 'Harikesha' is present in the last line of the Ragamalika.

d. Poshaka/Raja and Devata (indirect) Mudra

The last line of the composition mentions 'Sri Chamaraja' and 'Mahishe' referring to the ruler of Mysore and their tutelary deity 'Goddess Chamundeshwari'

e. Theme (Navavarana) and Prabandha Mudra

There are two instances where there is a reference to the theme of this composition, Navavarana,

- in the Pallavi as - 'navAvaraNa' shubha gAnakrtau
- in the last Charanam as - 'navAvaraNa' shrI rAga mAIAm navAM

And also the **Prabandha Mudra** is reflected in this same line as 'Raga Maalaam'. It is a rare fact that the ragamalika form has been used as mudra (also used in Dikshitar's ragamalikas) in 'Ragamala' phrase in the mangalam in Sri raga as:

4.2 Prosodical beauties

a. **Dvitiyakshara Prasa** is maintained in most of the instances in this composition-

- (i) trailokyamohanacakraAdhIshvari tripurAdikoNagAte vibhAsvari
AlokamAtreNa aNimAdi dAyini ambA kumari mAmavatu bhavAni
- (ii) sarvAshApurakacakra nivAsinIM sAdhu bhava santApa vinAshinIm
nirvANasaukhyadAM nirmalAM trimUrtiM nIrajAsinIM bhaje
niranjanakIrtim

b. **Yati** (Adiprasa) is also used in many places.

- (i) **Svarnakarshana ganapate Suguna dhanaseema dayanidhe**
(ii) **Thrailokya mohana chakradheesvari Thripuradi konagadevi.**

c. **Antya prasa** is seen in

- (i) Sarvasapuraka chakra **nivasineem**
saadhu bhava santhaapa **vinaasineem.**

4.3 Structural aesthetics

We can observe in this composition, the presence of many madhyamakala and tara sthaya sancharas, which reveal the essence of each raga. Each section has a chittasvara in the same raga, 1 avarta in the madhyama kalam and 3/4th avartam in double the speed, and the last 1/4th avartam (which ends with a phrase 'sm,grsndpm,grs,nsg,m) in Dhanyasi to link it to pallavi in Dhanyasi. Sree ragam is an auspicious raga used for Mangalam and it is succeeded by a Viloma chittasvara, covering all the ragas used in the reverse order.

The rhythmical setting of the composition also reveals the goddess as seated in each chakra and moving accordingly. The picture of the grandeur and beauty is obtained from the dhatu as well as the maatu of this ragamalika.

5. Mystical aspects

The Tantra ideology has a correlation with human model of Chakra organisation and Tantric practices involve a combination and correlation between the Yantra worship and human body (Rao, Science of Sri Chakra). Sri Vidya mysticism believes that there are several supernatural powers which could be obtained by men by contemplating on the minor goddesses in the outer enclosures of the citadel, in the centre of which is seated the Supreme Goddess who is the embodiment of all powers, who alone can give deliverance from all evil, sorrow and give eternal beatitude.

Our Sastras say that the avarana devatas represent the different states of our mind while practising Sri Vidya and these are summarized below:

1. Bhupura	-	Prakata Yogini	-	Wakefulness.
2. The 16 petalled lotus	-	Gupta Yogini	-	Dream.
3. The eight petalled lotus	-	Guptatara Yogini	-	Profound sleep.
4. The fourteen triangles	-	Sampradaya Yogini	-	Deliberation on God.
5. Outer 10 triangles	-	Kulottirna Yogini	-	Proximity to the Guru.
6. The inner triangles	-	Nigarbha Yogini	-	Upadesa
7. The eight triangles	-	Rahasya Yogini	-	Meditation
8. Central triangle	-	Atirahasya Yogini	-	Profound meditation.
9. Bindu Parapatati	-	Rahasya Yogini	-	Savikalpa Samadhi

6. Conclusion

Through this musical piece, Bhagavata demonstrates the spiritual depth and cultural richness of Indian musical heritage, acting as a bridge between Tantra philosophy and classical music. This connection encourages further exploration and appreciation of the deep ties between spirituality, philosophy, and artistic expression within Indian classical music traditions.

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